

Development and characterization of novel metallic joint in power electronic device

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SUMMARY

Copper/Carbon composites are now considered as very good candidates to act as efficient heat sinks in power electronics. However, reliability of the whole device still depends on the characteristics of the links between each components of a microelectronic device. This work presents an alternative route to report DBC on a Cu/C heat sink using a thin metallic film deposited by an electrodeposition process.

Keywords: Cu/C composite, CTE, thermal conductivity, Tin electrodeposition

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, power electronic systems are made of many different materials linked together by solder joints (Figure 1). Among all the properties of materials, which are used to elaborate typical microelectronics devices (Si for electronic component, alumina and Copper for DBC, SnAgCu for solder joints and Copper for heat sink) the thermal conductivity (TC) and coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) are decisive.

Figure 1: Schematic cross section picture of a microelectronic device.

Bonding and joining of materials is essential for the product lifetime especially in power electronics. The use of solders containing Lead is not anymore possible since July 2006 and the adoption of the RoHS directive of the European Union. State of the art is Lead-free soldering between Silicon semiconductor and DBC and between DBC and heat spreading materials. Different types of alloys have then been developed like Cu/Sn or Cu/Ag [1,2].

For heat sink, Cu/C with adaptative CTE, can be used to substitute pure Cu and therefore limit or decrease the thermal stresses enduced during thermal cycling (cf. Table 1).

Table 1: Thermal conductivity and CTE of materials composing the power unit.

	Si	Al ₂ O ₃	Cu	Sn	Cu/C composite
λ (W/m ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹)	163	40	403	67	// : 360 ⊥ : 160
CTE (10 ⁻⁶ K ⁻¹)	4,1	8	17	23	// : 8 to 10

However, there are still differences between the coefficients of thermal expansion. The solder joint who linked heat sink and DBC concentrates then thermo-mechanical stresses that will affect the reliability of the system during heating and cooling steps.

Due to its corrosion resistance, non-toxicity, solderability, ductility and low cost, tin deposits are widely used in the food industry and shipping equipment. In our case tin is considered as a good substitute for tin-lead coatings in electronic industry.

However, it is known that Tin-based solders are continuously degrading due to the growing intermetallic phases in the joining layer at ambient temperature. The degradation is rapidly increasing when the used temperature is increasing (homolog temperature, $T_{\text{experimental}}/T_{\text{melting}} > 0,6$) and increases even more during large change of temperature ($\Delta T > 50$ K). Also, in order to prevent the presence of voids inside the solder joint (thickness close to 200 μm), vacuum method can be used which increase the global price of the microelectronic device.

Promising technical solution for bonding and joining steps can be the pressure sintering of micro or nanosized silver powders (respectively paste). The main goals that are looked for are:

- reducing thickness of the solder joint
- reducing or preventing chemical reaction between Copper and the joining materials
- simplifying the joining technique (increasing reliability and decreasing global price of the device)

In this work, we propose to solve these 3 issues by working on a pure Tin film ($e \approx 1\mu\text{m}$ or less) which can be easily deposit on one or two surfaces by an electrodeposition method. Then a low temperature pressure method can lead to a strong and non-evolutive layer.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The heat sink is composed of pure Copper layers and one composite part (multilayer Cu-Cu/C-Cu respectively 0,4-2,4-0,4 mm thickness). In order to elaborate the composite, electrolytic Cu powders are mixed with carbon fibres (Fig.2) with different percentage volume ratio (from 0 up to 40 wt %). Then, this powder mixture is embedded in between two pure Copper powder layers and uniaxially hot pressed under controlled atmosphere (low vacuum, 650°C and 70 MPa) or hot extruded. The obtained heat sink can be annealed for relaxing intern stresses and promote microstructure evolution.

For the electrodeposition process, stannous sulphate (SnSO_4) was chosen for its better solubility in water than SnCl_2 . SnSO_4 also prevents chloride to pollute the bath and the deposit. The chosen electrolyte is dilute H_2SO_4 solution (37%) and some additives (ENTHONE®) are used to improve electrodeposit adhesion.

Electrodeposition process and interphase characterization

Thin Sn films are deposited on Copper substrates (DBC or bulk Cu-Cu/C-Cu) by an electrodeposition process performed at ambient temperature. A two-electrode cell (Pt grid anode and the substrate acting as a cathode) is controlled with an electronic potentiostat (TACUSSEL PRT-20-2, 20V, 2A) to establish a current density of $i = 2 \text{ A/dm}^2$ during 1 minutes in the stannous bath.

To obtain a good deposition process, the effect of different products concentrations has been investigated to optimise the dissolution of all components. The optimal composition is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: composition of the used stannous bath.

	SnSO ₄	H ₂ SO ₄	Brightener additive	Grain refiner additive
Concentration (g/L)	80	160	40	40

Theoretically deposit mass, m , can be estimated from the Faraday's Law (considering that the deposit is dense):

$$m = (1/nF).M.I.t.$$

where n is the oxidation state of metal; F the Faraday's constant; M the atomic weight of metal; I the current intensity in ampere and t the time in seconds. The average thickness can be formulate by a theoretical approach using the density ρ :

$$e_m = m/(\rho.S) = M.t.i/(n.F.\rho.S)$$

In the case of Sn and using the previous experimental conditions, e_m values were between 0.2 and 1 micron were obtained. Evaluations of the thickness and the composition of the deposit were realized by Auger Electron Spectroscopy (AES VG Microlab 310F) using Argon etching to realize depth profiles. A scanning electron microscope (SEM) JEOL JSM 6360A was used for the observation of the sample cross-sections. In addition, energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), which is attached to the SEM, was used to determinate the chemical composition.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

AES depth profiles have been performed on thin Tin films grown by electrolytic process on Cu-Cu/C-Cu materials with the previous experimental conditions. An example is given in Fig.3 and it can be seen that the thickness of the film is close to 0,15 μm and is totally free of Oxygen. AES spectra deconvolution showed that the width of the interfacial zone is only related to non-planar substrate surface.

Indeed, Copper reacts with Tin to form IMC's (Cu₆Sn₅ and Cu₃Sn) which induce compressive stresses and Sn whiskers growth [3-5]. But this phenomenon is very important only if the deposit is in contact with air. There is a flux of vacancies going from the free surface of the deposit towards the IMC/Sn interface. This stress creates a Sn atoms flux compensation which goes to the free surface via grain boundaries in order to release intern compression.

Figure 3: AES depth profile of sample surface of pure Cu after Sn electrodeposition.

Heat sink and DBC joining

DBC-to-heat sink joining has been done by a hot-press process performed in air (260°C, $P < 1 \text{ MPa}$) using thin glycerol protection film in between the two surfaces to prevent Sn oxidation during the joining process (cf. Fig.4). After investigations, we find that adhesion can be obtained only when Tin has been deposited on the two contact faces. In our experimental conditions, diffusion between Tin and Cu is too slow to allow IMC formation.

Figure 4: schematic system of the hot-joining technique.

Bonding is actually obtained the heat sink and DBC through the liquid Sn. However the film is not completely continuous, presenting some voids (Fig. 5).

Finally materials cross-sectioned have been prepared in order to characterize the interfacial microstructure. Fig. 5 shows two electron back-scattered micrographs (with different magnification) of such an interface. Voids are still present in the joining film showing a non-perfect diffusion of the Tin during the hot-joining process. These pores can be attributed to some glycerol traces which are not eliminated during the process. Tensile test have also been performed in order to know the adhesion force between the DBC and Cu-Cu/C-Cu heat sink. A value of about 2 MPa has been measured for that specific sample.

Figure 5: BSE micrograph of two copper substrates tin coated which are joining under few pressure under ambient atmosphere during 1 minute at 255°C.

CONCLUSION

A new joining technique between DBC and heat sink has been investigated using thin Tin film deposited by an electrolytic process. A uniform pure thin Tin layer of thickness close to 0.5 μm can be obtained. Experiments conditions for this new joining process are being investigated. Preventing oxidation of the Tin layer during the hot process needs to use an organic compound, such as glycerol, between the two surfaces but it leads to a porous interface. To prevent this phenomenon, vacuum chamber will be used. This new appliance, combined with the no-using of glycerol, should allow us to obtain stronger Sn/Sn interface.

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